

EFFECT OF BACK PAIN ON ACTIVITIES OF DAILY LIVING AMONG FEMALE NURSES IN PUNJAB, PAKISTAN

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Abstract

Background: Back pain is a common occupational health concern among healthcare professionals, with nurses experiencing a particularly high prevalence. **Materials and Methods:** To assess the occurrence of low back pain, its contributing factors, and its impact on daily living activities, a descriptive, correlational study was conducted among female nurses working in Punjab Institute of Neurosciences, Lahore. A total of 192 nurses participated, and data were collected electronically using a structured questionnaire along with the Oswestry Disability Index. **Results:** The findings revealed that 79% of the participants reported experiencing back pain. Disability scores indicated that the majority of female nurses suffered from moderate to severe disability levels. Furthermore, results showed a significant positive correlation between disability and the duration and severity of back pain. **Conclusion:** The study concludes that low back pain is highly prevalent among female nurses, significantly affecting their daily activities and necessitating targeted preventive and management strategies.

INTRODUCTION

Low back pain (LBP) is recognized as one of the most widespread musculoskeletal disorders and a leading cause of disability worldwide. According to the *Global Burden of Disease Study 2021*, an estimated 619 million people were living with LBP in 2020, and this number is projected to rise to more than 800 million by 2050 (GBD 2021 Low Back Pain Collaborators, 2023). Similarly, the World Health Organization (2023) highlights that LBP is a major contributor to activity limitations and decreased quality of life among working-age adults. These statistics underscore the urgent need to address LBP, particularly among high-risk occupational groups such as nurses, who are frequently exposed to factors that predispose them to musculoskeletal problems.

Nurses face a disproportionately high risk of developing LBP due to the physical demands of their profession, including frequent patient handling, prolonged standing, awkward postures, and repetitive bending and lifting (Ovayolu et al., 2014). Systematic reviews have reported a high 12-month prevalence of LBP among nurses, often ranging between 50% and 80% globally (Kasa et al., 2020). In China, a multicenter cross-sectional study demonstrated that the majority of nurses reported inadequate occupational prevention practices for LBP, linking the burden to workload intensity and limited access to preventive training (Liu et al., 2023). These findings suggest that beyond physical strain, gaps in institutional support and ergonomic training further

exacerbate the risk of back pain and its associated disabilities.

In Pakistan, the burden of work-related musculoskeletal disorders among nurses is similarly concerning. A survey conducted in different hospitals revealed that LBP was the most common musculoskeletal complaint among nurses, largely attributed to poor posture, heavy workload, and manual patient handling (Rathore et al., 2017). A recent study from Lahore further reported that frontline healthcare workers, especially nurses, frequently experienced LBP, with contributing factors including long working hours, inadequate rest, and heavy patient lifting (Sultana et al., 2023). The functional impact of this condition can be effectively assessed through standardized tools such as the Oswestry Disability Index (Fairbank & Pynsent, 2000), which measures disability related to activities of daily living (ADLs). Therefore, examining the effect of LBP on ADLs among nurses in Punjab is crucial for developing effective ergonomic, educational, and policy interventions.

1. Materials and Methods

This study employed a **descriptive, correlational design** and was conducted at the *Punjab Institute of Neurosciences, Lahore*, a tertiary-level hospital. The target population consisted of female **nurses working in the institute**. For a total population of 392 female nurses, with a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin

of error, the required sample size calculated using the Raosoft formula is 192 female nurses.

The sampling process was carried out in two stages. First, **cluster sampling** was applied by categorizing hospital units based on their functional areas. Critical care and high-risk departments such as neurosurgery, neurology, neuropsychiatry, and neurorehabilitation **wards** were selected. In the second stage, female nurses working in these units were **invited conveniently** to participate.

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of the *Punjab Institute of Neurosciences, Lahore*. An explanatory note was attached to the online questionnaire, ensuring participants that their participation was voluntary, data confidentiality would be maintained, and withdrawal was allowed at any stage without penalty. The researcher's contact email was provided for any queries.

Data were collected using a **self-developed questionnaire** based on an extensive literature review and supplemented by the **Oswestry Disability Index (Fairbank & Pynsent, 2000)** to measure the impact of back pain on activities of daily living. The questionnaire link was distributed electronically. The data collection process spanned **two months** and included periodic follow-ups to enhance response rates. The collected data were analyzed using **SPSS version 24** for descriptive and correlational statistics.

2. Results

Table 1. Background Characteristics of Participants (N = 192)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age	< 25 years	6	3.1
	25-30 years	88	45.8
	31-35 years	33	17.2
	36-40 years	29	15.1
	41-45 years	18	9.4
	> 45 years	18	9.4
Marital Status	Single	70	36.5
	Married	122	63.5
Educational Background	BSN	154	80.2
	MSN	38	19.8
Work Experience	< 1 year	8	4.2
	1-5 years	69	35.9
	6-10 years	48	25.0

	11-15 years	38	19.8
	16-20 years	29	15.1
Working Shifts	Morning	41	21.4
	Evening	5	2.6
	All Shifts	146	76.0
Exercise Program	Never	110	57.3
	1-2 times/week	62	32.3
	3-4 times/week	13	6.8
	> 4 times/week	7	3.6
Body Mass Index (BMI)	< 18 (Underweight)	17	8.9
	18.5-25 (Normal)	121	63.0
	26-30 (Overweight)	44	22.9
	> 30 (Obese)	10	5.2

The study included a total of 192 nurses. The majority of participants were young adults, with 45.8% aged 25-30 years, followed by 17.2% between 31-35 years, and 15.1% between 36-40 years. A smaller proportion were 41-45 years (9.4%) and above 45 years (9.4%), while only 3.1% were below 25 years.

In terms of marital status, nearly two-thirds of the participants were married (63.5%), while 36.5% were single. Regarding educational background, the majority held a Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN, 80.2%), while 19.8% had a Master of Science in Nursing (MSN) degree.

The work experience profile showed that 35.9% of nurses had 1-5 years of professional experience, followed by 25.0% with 6-10 years, and 19.8% with

11-15 years. About 15.1% had 16-20 years of experience, while 4.2% were relatively new with less than 1 year of service.

With respect to working shifts, the majority (76.0%) worked rotational/all shifts, while 21.4% worked morning shifts and only 2.6% worked evening shifts exclusively. In terms of exercise habits, more than half of the nurses (57.3%) reported never engaging in exercise, while 32.3% exercised 1-2 times per week, and smaller proportions exercised 3-4 times (6.8%) or more than 4 times (3.6%) per week.

Considering Body Mass Index (BMI), the majority of participants had a normal weight (63.0%), while 22.9% were overweight, and 5.2% were obese. A minority of 8.9% were underweight.

Table 2. Characteristics of Back Pain among Female Nurses (N = 192)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Back Pain Present	No	40	20.8
	Yes	152	79.2
Duration of Back Pain	1-3 years	141	73.4
	4-6 years	40	20.8
	7-10 years	7	3.6
	> 10 years	4	2.1
Severity of Back Pain	Mild (1-3)	127	66.1
	Moderate (4-6)	60	31.3
	Severe (7-10)	5	2.6
Causes of Back Pain	Injury	11	5.7
	Sudden Movement	11	5.7
	Disease	3	1.6
	Load Lifting	42	21.9
	Bad Posture	11	5.7

	Work Overload	107	55.7
	Other	7	3.7
Relieving Back Pain	Pain Killers	56	29.2
	Relaxation	70	36.5
	Bed Rest	63	32.8
	Other	3	1.5
Sick Leaves due to Back Pain	No	168	87.5
	Yes	24	12.5

Among the 192 nurses, the prevalence of back pain was high, with **79.2% reporting back pain** and only **20.8% reporting none**. The majority of those affected had been experiencing pain for **1–3 years (73.4%)**, followed by **4–6 years (20.8%)**, while only a small proportion reported pain lasting **7–10 years (3.6%)** or more than 10 years (2.1%). In terms of severity, most nurses described their pain as **mild (66.1%)**, nearly one-third as **moderate (31.3%)**, and a small fraction as **severe (2.6%)**. The leading reported cause of back pain

was **work overload (55.7%)**, followed by **load lifting (21.9%)**, while smaller proportions attributed it to **injury, sudden movement, or bad posture (5.7% each)**, **disease (1.6%)**, or other causes (3.7%). To relieve back pain, nurses most commonly used **relaxation (36.5%)**, **bed rest (32.8%)**, or **painkillers (29.2%)**, while very few relied on other methods (1.5%). Additionally, **12.5% reported taking sick leave due to back pain**, whereas the majority (87.5%) continued working despite their condition.

Table 3. Work-Related and Organizational Factors Associated with Back Pain (N = 192)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Use of Aiding Materials During Care	No	147	76.6
	Yes	45	23.4
Received Education on Body Mechanics	No	65	33.9
	Yes	127	66.1
Frequent Bending Activities	No	48	25.0
	Yes	144	75.0
Heavy Lifting	No	48	25.0
	Yes	144	75.0
Sustained Sitting (> 30 min)	No	95	49.5
	Yes	97	50.5
Prolonged Standing (> 1 hour)	No	28	14.6
	Yes	164	85.4
Lifting/Transferring Patients	No	26	13.5
	Yes	166	86.5
Positioning Patients on Bed	No	28	14.6
	Yes	164	85.4
Night Shift Work	No	55	28.6
	Yes	137	71.4
Poor Working Environment	No	78	40.6
	Yes	114	59.4
Physical Activities at Work	No	41	21.4
	Yes	151	78.6
Inadequate Rest Intervals	No	53	27.6

	Yes	139	72.4
Staff Shortage	No	22	11.5
	Yes	170	88.5
High Number of Patients Handled	No	49	25.5
	Yes	143	74.5
Work Satisfaction	No	73	38.0
	Yes	119	62.0
Support from Colleagues	No	131	68.2
	Yes	61	31.8
Support from Supervisor/Manager	No	105	54.7
	Yes	87	45.3

Among the 192 nurses, the majority reported **not using aiding devices during care (76.6%)**, though two-thirds (66.1%) had received education on proper body mechanics. Most participants engaged in **frequent bending (75.0%)**, **heavy lifting (75.0%)**, and **prolonged standing (85.4%)**, while 86.5% were involved in **lifting or transferring patients** and 85.4% in **positioning patients on beds**. More than two-thirds

worked **night shifts (71.4%)**, and over half (59.4%) reported a **poor working environment**. A large proportion also faced **staff shortages (88.5%)**, **inadequate rest intervals (72.4%)**, and **high patient loads (74.5%)**. Despite these challenges, 62.0% expressed **work satisfaction**, though most cited **limited support from colleagues (68.2%)** and **supervisors (54.7%)**.

Table 4. Oswestry Disability Index Scores (N = 192)

Score Range	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
0–20 (Minimal Disability)	34	17.7
21–40 (Moderate Disability)	93	48.4
41–60 (Severe Disability)	53	27.6
61–80 (Crippling Disability)	11	5.7
81–100 (Bed-bound/Exaggerated)	1	0.6
Total	192	100

Based on the Oswestry Disability Index (ODI) scores of 192 nurses, the majority experienced some level of functional limitation. Nearly half of the participants (48.4%) fell within the **moderate disability range (21–40)**, while more than one-quarter (27.6%) reported **severe disability (41–60)**. A smaller proportion (17.7%) had **minimal disability (0–20)**, whereas 5.7%

reported **crippling disability (61–80)**. Only 0.6% of the sample scored in the **bed-bound/exaggerated disability range (81–100)**. These findings indicate that most nurses suffered from **moderate to severe disability** due to back pain, highlighting its substantial impact on their daily functioning and quality of life.

Table 5. Spearman Correlation between Demographic, Work-Related Factors, Back Pain Characteristics and Disability Score (N = 192)

Variable	Spearman's r	p-value	Relationship
Demographic Factors			
Experience	0.10	= .05	Positive
Working hours	0.19	< .01	Positive
Educational background	-0.14	< .01	Negative

Back Pain Characteristics			
Presence of back pain	0.40	< .01	Positive
Duration of back pain	0.22	< .01	Positive
Severity of back pain	0.45	< .01	Positive
Sick leaves due to back pain	0.28	< .01	Positive
Work-Related Factors			
Use of aid materials	0.16	< .01	Positive
Poor working environment	0.21	< .01	Positive
Staff shortage	0.24	< .01	Positive
Support from colleague	0.18	< .01	Positive
Support from supervisor/manager	0.20	< .01	Positive

The correlation analysis revealed that among demographic factors, **experience** ($r = 0.10$, $p = .05$) and **working hours** ($r = 0.19$, $p < .01$) were positively associated with disability scores, while **educational background** ($r = -0.14$, $p < .01$) showed a negative association. Regarding back pain characteristics, the **presence of back pain** ($r = 0.40$, $p < .01$), its **duration** ($r = 0.22$, $p < .01$), **severity** ($r = 0.45$, $p < .01$), and **sick leaves due to back pain** ($r = 0.28$, $p < .01$) were all positively related to disability scores, with severity showing the strongest association. Work-related factors such as **use of aid materials** ($r = 0.16$, $p < .01$), **poor working environment** ($r = 0.21$, $p < .01$), **staff shortage** ($r = 0.24$, $p < .01$), **support from colleagues** ($r = 0.18$, $p < .01$), and **support from supervisors** ($r = 0.20$, $p < .01$) were also positively correlated with disability scores, indicating that both occupational demands and organizational conditions contribute significantly to functional disability among nurses.

3. Discussion

The present study reveals a notably high prevalence of back pain (79.2%) among nurses, with a significant proportion experiencing moderate to severe disability as measured by the Oswestry Disability Index. This pattern aligns with a recent investigation into Pakistani nursing populations, which similarly highlighted both the high frequency of low back pain and its substantial impact on functional ability (Ijabadeniyi, 2023). Moreover, the observed positive correlations between disability scores and factors such as working hours, presence and severity of pain, and sick leave are consistent with prior evidence. For instance, studies in Pakistan have found that longer shifts and increased physical demands contribute

markedly to back pain and functional limitations among nurses (Ijabadeniyi, 2023; Zafar et al., 2023). These occupational stressors compound the risk for sustained disability, underlining the need for workload and shift distribution interventions.

Interestingly, our finding that higher educational background (MSN) is negatively associated with disability suggests that advanced training may afford protective benefits—potentially by enhancing ergonomics knowledge or self-care awareness. Although there is limited direct evidence in nursing, increased education has been associated with greater personal agency and better coping strategies in other health-related contexts (Narrative Review of Factors Affecting Lower Back Pain Among Workers in Pakistan, 2022). The dominance of work overload (55.7%) as a reported cause of back pain in our sample underscores the role of organizational and ergonomic risk factors. This is echoed across the literature, where factors like prolonged standing, manual lifting, and poor institutional support are routinely flagged as key contributors to low back pain (Narrative Review, 2022).

Finally, while our study did not directly quantify the impact of psychological factors such as stress and mood, the significant correlations between disability and elements like poor work environment and inadequate support echo the biopsychosocial model of pain. Research from other settings underscores that low back pain is not merely biomechanical but is influenced by psychosocial stressors, job dissatisfaction, and supportive culture at work (Tosunoz & Oztunc, 2020).

4. Conclusion

The study concludes that low back pain is highly prevalent among female nurses, with most experiencing moderate to severe disability that significantly affects their daily functioning. Targeted interventions, including workload management, ergonomic training, and organizational support, are essential to reduce the burden and improve nurses' quality of life.

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